

PERFORATION CHARACTERISTICS OF FABRICS MADE OF HIGH STRENGTH PE FIBERS

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SUMMARY: Perforation study was performed for textile fabrics made of high strength PE fibers to study effects of textile structure, strand twisting and fiber surface treatment on perforation energy, i.e., fabrics resistance at perforation. An air gun facility was used to accelerate a steel bullet in a velocity range 50-200 m/s. High speed photography was performed to observe high speed deformation of specimen cloth until breakage. The results shows that two kinds of perforation modes exist depending on the textile structure, and the perforation energy depends on the bullet velocity.

KEYWORDS: polyethylene, fabrics, ballistic impact, perforation

INTRODUCTION

Textile fabrics made of high strength fibers have been widely used for industrial and leisure purposes. As the textile fabrics are regarded as high impact materials, they have been utilized to protect mankind under the conditions in which people may be injured by projectiles. For example, specially designed clothes such as space suits and bulletproof jackets are made from high impact textile fabrics. Therefore, it is important to understand the impact resistance of fabrics to know the limit of such clothes and to improve their properties. Also, fabric composites have been developed by impregnating fabrics into resins. Therefore, it is useful to characterize the impact properties of fabrics to know the impact resistance of the composites.

Aramid fibers such as Kevlar 29 and 49 have been widely used for high impact clothes, while high strength polyethylene (PE) fibers have been also developed. Since some of PE fibers have lower density and higher strength than the aramid fibers, the PE fibers may have an advantage over the aramid fibers as fabrics for high impact clothes.

A few attempts have been made to study impact performance of textile fabrics. Montgomery studied the effects of the shape of projectiles on impact energy absorbed by fabrics [1,2]. Wilde et al. studied impact performance of fabrics based on high speed photography [3,4]. Recently, Morrison et al. investigated the perforation phenomena of aramid laminates [5]. On the other hand, Leech et al. studied impact behavior of cloths and nets by projectile theoretically, and proposed a model to explain the behavior [6].

In the above studies, the velocities of the projectiles were in the range of several hundred meter per second. On the other hand, in the present study, impact testing was performed at relatively low bullet velocities (<200 m/s). Dependence of the bullet velocity on the perforation energy absorbed by PE cloths was mainly investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

High strength polyethylene cloths tested in the present study are shown in Table 1. In Table 1, surface treatment means that the oil used during the process of fiber forming is removed. Photographs of typical cloth surfaces and schematic drawings of the corresponding textile structures are shown in Fig.1. The mechanical properties of the row fiber which is used for the fabrication of cloth, are as follows:

density: 0.98 g/cm², tensile strength: 2.92 GPa, tensile modulus: 137 GPa.

Air Gun

A multipurpose air gun was used for the impact testing and the testing facility is shown in Fig.2. The air gun consists of a high pressure vessel, a launcher barrel and a low pressure vessel in which cloth specimen is held. The length of the whole apparatus is 4,000 mm. High pressurized air of 5 liter up to 150 atm can be filled up in the high pressure vessel using air compressor or high pressure gas cylinder. The inner diameter and the length of the launcher barrel are 25 mm and 2,000 mm, respectively. The diameter and the length of the low pressure vessel are 600 mm and 1,100 mm, respectively, and the inside pressure is reduced to about 10⁻² torr. This vessel has two pairs of window for observation. The projectile (sabot) used for the present study is made of polyethylene, and the geometry is shown in Fig.3.

Measurement of Bullet Velocity and High Speed Photography

The whole system for the measurement of bullet velocity and high speed photography is shown in Fig.4. A chrome steel bullet (9.5 mm diameter and 3.55 g mass) is placed in the front of the polyethylene sabot, and the accelerated sabot stops at the sabot stopper placed at the end of the launcher barrel. As a result, only the steel bullet flies and collides against cloth specimen. The bullet velocity V_i before the collision is measured from the time difference when the bullet crosses over the two laser lights as shown in Fig.4. The deformation process of the cloth specimen after the collision and the bullet velocity V_o after the perforation are obtained using multiplex photography with transmitted light pulse emanated from the multi-flash.

Absorbed Perforation Energy

If a steel bullet collides against cloth specimen at velocity V_i and the velocity reduces to V_o after perforation, then the perforation energy absorbed by the cloth can be estimated from the difference of the kinetic energy of the bullet before and after the perforation, i.e.

$$E_i - E_o = \frac{1}{2} m (V_i^2 - V_o^2) \quad (1)$$

where E_i and E_o are the kinetic energies before and after the perforation, respectively, and m the mass of the steel bullet.

Fixation of Cloth Specimen

Cloth specimen is fixed perpendicular to the direction of bullet flight and the bullet collides at the center of the cloth. Detail of the specimen fixture is shown in Fig.5 (1). An example of cloth specimen after impact test is also shown in Fig.5 (2). Figs.5(3) and (4) show the two-dimensional distribution of elongation for unperforated cloth A obtained at $V_i = 59.9$ m/s, and Fig.5(5) show the side view of the same specimen just after the impact. The side view of perforated cloth A obtained at $V_i = 76.8$ m/s is shown in Fig.5 (6).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

High Speed Photography

Typical examples of high speed photography are shown in Fig.6(a) for cloth A and Fig.6(b) for cloth B. In the caption of Fig.6, *PI* expresses the interval of light pulses. For both cloth A and B, the figure (1) shows an unperforated result photographed at a velocity very close to the critical velocity at which perforation occurs. The figures (2), (3) and (4) show perforated results obtained at higher impact velocities. It is clearly seen from Fig.6 that for cloth A, the yarns are cut off completely and there is no pull-out of yarn after the perforation; on the other hand, the steel bullet perforates through the cloth B pulling out several yarns. It is also noted that for cloth B, different pull-out modes can be observed depending on the velocity V_i . In the present study, cloths A, A' and D show the same tendency of perforation with cutting of yarns as shown in Fig.6(a). On the other hand, for cloths B, B', C and E, steel bullet perforates through each cloth accompanied with pull-out of yarns as shown in Fig.6(b).

Critical Perforation Velocity and Critical Perforation Energy

When a steel bullet collides a cloth specimen, the bullet cannot perforate through the cloth at the velocities lower than a critical value of impact velocity. The bullet perforates through the cloth when the impact velocity reaches a higher value than the critical velocity. This critical velocity is called the critical perforation velocity V_{ic} and the corresponding energy absorbed by cloth is called the critical perforation energy E_c . For each cloth, V_{ic} and E_c are shown in Fig.7 and Fig.8, respectively. The results shown in Fig.7 and 8 are very useful to estimate the perforation resistance of each cloth. However, these results may not present enough information to compare the perforation energies absorbed by the cloths which have different conditions such as the size of yarn, strand twisting, textile structure and raw material. In this study, the specific perforation energy is defined by

$$E_R = E_c / W_R \quad (2)$$

where W_R is the areal weight density, which is the weight of cloth per 1 m^2 . For each cloth, E_R value is shown in Fig.9. Although E_R does not reflect the effect of each of the above conditions on the perforation energy, it is a convenient method to evaluate the perforation energy from comprehensive point of view.

The followings are obtained from the data for the specific perforation energy E_R .

(1) Effect of surface treatment

Treated cloth absorbs larger energy than untreated one even if the yarn size, the number of twists, the textile structure and the areal weight density are the same in both cloths. It appears that this is mainly because the frictional force between yarns in the treated cloth becomes larger than in the untreated one owing to the removal of oil used during fiber forming process.

(2) Relation between the areal weight density and perforation energy

Regarding plain woven untreated polyethylene fiber cloth, the specific perforation energy absorbed by cloth A is much lower than those of cloths C, D and E as shown in Fig.9. The difference of the mean values is approximately 10 J/kg/m^2 . The critical perforation energy E_C is shown as a function of the areal weight density W_R in Fig.10. A linear relation between E_C and W_R is observed in Fig.10. It is also observed that E_C of cloth A is lower than that of cloth D, although both cloths have the almost same W_R value. It may be understood that this is due to the effect of the number of twists considering that the other conditions are the same in both cloths. Thus, it is expected that the number of twists, 160 times/m, for cloth D gives higher E_C value than 80 times/m for cloth A.

On the other hand, the E_C value of basket woven untreated polyethylene cloth B is lower by 20 % than the extrapolated value of the plain woven untreated cloths. It is expected that a group of basket woven cloths also has a linear relation between E_C and W_R , and a straight line situated at a lower position than the line for the plain woven cloths may be drawn in Fig.10. This is further discussed in the following.

(3) Relation between the difference of textile structure and perforation energy

As described above, the perforation energy absorbed by plain woven cloth is larger than that absorbed by basket woven cloth. This relation may originate in the difference of textile structure. By comparing plain woven and basket woven cloths, in which the size of yarn and the yarn density are the same, it can be said that the frictional force between yarns in plain woven cloth is larger than in basket woven cloth, because the number of the crossing points of warp and fill for plain woven cloth are four times that for basket woven cloth. This results in the larger perforation energy absorbed by plain woven cloth.

Dependence of Perforation Energy on V_i

It is interesting to know the V_i -dependence of the perforation energy absorbed by cloth when steel bullet collides the cloth at relatively low velocities ($\leq 200 \text{ m/s}$) exceeding the critical perforation velocity. Dependence of the perforation energy, $E_i - E_o$, on V_i is shown in Fig.11. Fig.11 (a) shows the classification of marks used in the figures (b)-(h). The figures (b), (c) and (g) show the examples of the case in which steel bullet cuts off the yarns. On the other hand, the figures (d), (e), (f) and (h) show the examples of the case in which steel bullet perforates through the cloth accompanied with the pull-out of yarns. From these experimental results, the following can be shown with respect to V_i -dependence of perforation energy.

(1) Relation between the difference of pull-out modes and perforation energy

Perforation energy absorbed by cloth depends on the pull-out mode, i.e. the number of yarns pulled out. In general, larger number of pull-out results in larger absorbed perforation energy.

(2) V_i -dependence of perforation energy

Perforation energy of polyethylene cloth tends to increase with increase of V_i in a certain range of velocity greater than the critical velocity and decrease at higher velocities. However, for cloth B (Fig.11(d)) and cloth E (Fig.11(h)), wide scatters are observed in the data because the perforation energy varies with the pull-out mode. In general, the perforation energy tends to increase with increasing V_i . In Figs.11(d) and (h), V_i -dependence of the perforation energy is not clear for the velocities greater than 200 m/s. Considering the V_i -dependency of the other cloths, it is expected that for cloth B and E, the perforation energy also decreases with increase of V_i for $V_i > 200$ m/s, and then reaches a constant value. This V_i -dependency appears to depend on the shape and size of projectiles and the range of the impact velocity [2].

Generally, absorbed perforation energy by cloth due to the collision of steel bullet depends on the way of the specimen fixation and the mechanical properties of the row fibers. It is also considered that the pull-out resistance of yarn, the change of textile density generated by the collision and the microdamage morphology of yarn and filament including heat effects have influence on the perforation energy. A further study is needed for understanding the detailed mechanisms.

CONCLUSIONS

Perforation study of high strength polyethylene fiber cloths was performed in a velocity range 50-200 m/s using an air gun facility. The followings have been shown by the study.

1. The perforation energy initially increases linearly with increase of the bullet velocity. However, it tends to decrease over a limit which is around at 150 m/s.
2. The critical perforation energy, which is defined as the minimum energy required to cause perforation, can be shown as a linear function of areal weight density of fabrics.
3. Two kinds of perforation modes, that is, cutting of yarns and pull-out of yarns are observed depending on the textile structure.
4. Effects of fiber surface treatment as well as of strand twisting are shown to exist.

REFERENCES

1. T.G. Montgomery, PhD Thesis, 1980, North Carolina State University.
2. T.G. Montgomery, P.L. Grady and C. Tomasino, Textile Research Journal, 52 (1982), 442.
3. A.F. Wilde, Textile Res. J., 44 (1974) 772.
4. A.F. Wilde, J.J. Ricca, J.M. Rogers and L.M. Cole, Polym. Eng. Sci., 12 (1972) 41.
5. C.E. Morrison and W. H. Bowyer, Proc. ICCM 2, (1980) 233.
6. C. Leech, J.W.S. Hearle and J. Mansell, J. Text. Inst., 70 (1979) 469.

Table 1: Characteristics of cloth specimens

Specimen	Yarn		WD* ¹ (per inch)	Twisting* ² (times/m)	Textile structure	AWD* ³ (kg/m ²)	Surface treatment	Thickness (mm)
	Denier	Filament						
A	300	300	50	160	plain weave	0.146	untreated	0.27
A'	300	300	50	160	plain weave	0.146	treated	0.27
B	1160	960	35	80(W) 0(F)	2x2 basket	0.411	untreated	0.71
B'	1160	960	35	80(W) 0(F)	2x2 basket	0.411	treated	0.75
C	800	795	36	70(W)90(F)	plain weave	0.280	untreated	0.50
D	300	280	50	80	plain weave	0.144	untreated	0.29
E	600		34	45	plain weave	0.215	untreated	0.39

*¹ WD is the weave density.

*² W and F are the warp and fill, respectively.

*³ AWD is the areal weight density.

Fig.1: Multipurpose air gun facility

Fig.2: Geometry of projectile (sabot)

Fig.3: System for the measurement of bullet velocity and high speed photography

Fig.4: (1) specimen fixture, (2) cloth specimen after impact, (3, 4, 5) deformation of unperforated cloth specimen for $V_i=59.9$ m/s and (6) perforated specimen for $V_i=76.8$ m/s

Fig.5: Textile structures of typical cloth specimens

Fig.6: (a) deformation and perforation mode of cloth A ((1) $V_i=59.9$ m/s, $PI=150$ μ s, (2) $V_i=90.7$ m/s, $V_o=37.7$ m/s, $PI=150$ μ s, (3) $V_i=136.5$ m/s, $V_o=100.3$ m/s, $PI=100$ μ s and (4) $V_i=147.5$ m/s, $V_o=122.7$ m/s, $PI=100$ μ s) and (b) deformation and perforation mode of cloth B ((1) $V_i=105.1$ m/s, $PI=150$ μ s, (2) $V_i=134.3$ m/s, $V_o=82.7$ m/s, $PI=150$ μ s, (3) $V_i=160.0$ m/s, $V_o=107.6$ m/s, $PI=100$ μ s and (4) $V_i=172.8$ m/s, $V_o=112.3$ m/s, $PI=100$ μ s)

Fig.7: Critical perforation velocity of cloth specimen

Fig.8: Critical perforation energy of cloth specimen

Fig.9: Specific perforation energy of cloth specimen

Fig.10: W_R - E_c relation of cloth specimen

	Mark	Perforation mode
Unperforated	X	
Perforated	○	○ ○ ○ ○
	●	○ ○ ○ ○
	●	○ ○ ○ ○
	⊙	○ ○ ○ ○

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

Fig. 11: Dependence of perforation energy on V_i